

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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PERIOPERATIVE HAND OFF: A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the Degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The peri-operative arena is a complex environment where multiple tasks occur such as preparing patients for surgery, monitoring patients for complications, and ensuring patient safety during transition of care. This management process requires continuous communication between providers to promote safe and effective care. Studies suggest that a standardized process of communicating specific information and data may optimize patient care during transition (De Vries et al., 2010).

A quality improvement (QI) project was conducted in an outpatient surgery setting. Its focus was to develop, implement, and evaluate a handoff tool that would serve as a checklist for the pre-operative and intra-operative nurses during transition of care. A 3-phase design was used. First, pre-data collection of errors was identified from occurrence reports. Second, a Pre-operative Checklist Tool (POCT) was developed and its content validity established. Third, the POCT was evaluated for reliability, effectiveness, compliance, and ease of use.

Results reflected that 76% of nurses surveyed reported that the POCT contained appropriate safety components. Most participants (78%) believed that the POCT would improve communication. Prior to POCT use, 14 monthly occurrence reports revealed that 1 to 3 negative clinical events occurred monthly. During the 1-month pilot and four months afterwards, there were no reported negative clinical events. This QI project supported the benefits of using a standardized communication process during care peri-operative transitions.

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INTRODUCTION

The perioperative arena is a complex healthcare environment where multiple tasks occur including preparing patients for surgery, monitoring patients for complications, and ensuring patient safety during transitions of care. This management process requires continuous communication between providers to promote safe and effective care. In comparison to patients in other hospital settings (emergency rooms, intensive care units, etc.) perioperative patients are at a higher risk for medical errors due to gaps and/or errors in communication (Chard & Makary, 2015). This vulnerability is linked to the transfer of patients through multiple and varied intra-operative phases and settings. Each phase requires a hand off of information tailored to the specific and often critical needs of an individual patient. It also involves communication among multiple staff members throughout the various points of care (Chard & Makary, 2015). Communication between health care professionals must be accurate and timely to ensure positive outcomes when transferring a patient from one level of care to another. When it does not occur, negative patient outcomes often result (Chard & Makary, 2015).

Studies suggest that a standardized process of communicating specific information and data may optimize the transition of patient care (De Vries et al., 2010). The use of a checklist to ensure standardized communication during the peri-operative care may be part of the solution to mitigate negative sequela from communication breakdowns. Haynes et al. (2009) conducted a study involving a sample of eight hospitals using the Peri-operative Safety Checklist based on the World Health Organization (WHO) Guidelines and Recommendations. The use of the Pre-operative Safety Checklist reduced surgical complications from 11% to 7 % by ensuring that

information was communicated between providers. Another study conducted by Salzwedel, Mai, Punke, Kluge, and Reuter (2016) concluded that by using a standardized hand off checklist during patient transition from one area to another increased the quantity and quality of transmitted clinical information.

Problem Statement

The project undertaken by the Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) author aimed to improve communication between staff in the peri-operative and intra-operative areas by developing, implementing, and evaluating a standardized communication tool (checklist) for use during transitions of care. The project took place in an outpatient setting in a hospital in southern California. The DNP author is employed at the project setting and reviewed fourteen months of data related to negative intra-operative events collected during the time frame of May 1, 2016 through July 31, 2017. The information was generated from the hospital's computer-based system of occurrence reporting. The reporting system divides negative outcomes into various categories (communication hand-off, documentation consents, etc.) based on predetermined labeling standardized by the hospital's Quality Department. The Clinical Risk Specialists from the Risk Department are responsible for categorizing each reported event. The category of communication breakdowns accounted for 47% (N=18) of the reported negative intra-operative outcomes (N=38) that occurred in the outpatient surgical center during May 1, 2016 through July 31, 2017, prior to the implementation of this project. Communication oversights primarily were associated with missing or inaccurate information. Typically this failure resulted from the lack of one caregiver communicating to the next caregiver important information needed for a safe transition of patient care.

Similar findings associated with communication breakdowns were noted when the data collected in the project's hospital inpatient operative setting were analyzed. Thirty-one percent of negative intra-operative occurrences were the result of ineffective communication. The negative impact of an intra-operative communication breakdown highlights the significance of this project. De Vries et al. (2010) demonstrated that an established standardized communication process between pre-operative and intra-operative staff is linked to improved communication. This standardization has resulted in a decrease of avoidable negative events. Therefore, this author sought to improve perioperative care by implementing an evidence-based hand off checklist tool to decrease communication breakdown.

Purpose Statement

In the practice setting of the DNP author, there were no standardized nurse-to-nurse communication processes between pre-operative and intra-operative care settings. Thus, the purpose of this DNP project was to create a process to improve nurse-to-nurse communication and reporting of critical patient information to ensure a safe transition between pre-operative and intra-operative settings. To achieve this aim, a standardized communication checklist was developed, implemented, and evaluated for use during the pre-operative through intra-operative phases of patient care.

Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework provides the structure, establishes the scope, and maps the entire process of the project (Bonnell & Smith, 2014). If a theoretical framework is not incorporated as part of the plan, the success of the nursing project may be jeopardized (Bonnell & Smith, 2014). The theoretical framework for this project is the Plan-Do-

Study-Act (PDSA) cycle (Figure 1). The PDSA cycle is a systematic series of steps, which allows for the continued evaluation of a change (The W. Edwards Deming Institute, 2016). This model is used at the author's place of employment when change is needed to improve patient care or work setting processes.

The PDSA cycle is also known by two other names, the Shewhart Cycle and the Deming Cycle (Johnson, 2002). Walter Shewhart believed that consistency in evaluation of practices and the desire of leadership to support ideas and adopt change are critical to the success of a project (Johnson, 2002). W. Edwards Deming originated the term Shewhart Cycle for Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) cycle. Many healthcare organizations use the PDSA model to facilitate the implementation of small practice changes (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2017).

The PDSA cycle includes four steps: Plan-Do-Study-Act. The Plan stage includes the identification of the purpose, collection of data, and defining the metrics of the project. The Do stage focuses on the implementation phase in the practice setting. The Study stage involves an evaluation of the practice change. The Act stage addresses activities related to the development of recommendations for further practice changes.

Integration of Theoretical Framework into the Project

The model began by asking three questions (IHI, 2017). First, what changes need to be accomplished? Second, how will the changes be evaluated to see if there is an actual improvement? Third, what changes can be performed that will result in improvement?

In the Plan stage for this project, data were collected about the problem. During this stage, identification of the stakeholders, resources, and objectives was completed. At

this stage, a literature review of Evidence-Based Practices (EBP) was conducted to identify how others have defined and measured key concepts of interest in this project. The literature review identified the essential components of the checklist and the educational program needed for the staff to implement the nurse-to-nurse checklist communication tool. The checklist and survey tools were developed by the DNP author in collaboration with the leadership and nursing staff of the outpatient surgery department at the project location. During this stage, the in-service education program was developed for nurses and geared towards the use of the checklist during the hand off process.

In the Do stage, the tool was reviewed and approved by an expert panel from the Surgical Safety Committee. Upon approval by the expert panel, the staff were educated through in-services about the checklist and the handoff process. The checklist was then implemented during patient hand off reports between pre-operative and intra-operative nurses. The use of the checklist tool involved a two-month pilot study beginning August 1, 2017 and ending September 30, 2017. During Phase I, the first month of the pilot study (August 1-August 31, 2017), data were collected to identify issues and barriers related to the use of the checklist. During Phase II, the second month of the pilot study (September 1-September 30, 2017), the nurses were instructed to continue using the checklist without collecting data. The purpose of continuing the hand off process was to maintain continuity until the completion of the Study stage. An audit was conducted on a daily basis by the DNP author and the nurse manager to ensure the checklist was used appropriately for all scheduled surgical cases. The weekly audits included tallying the number of surgical cases performed in the operating suites and comparing the number of

accurate patient checklists completed. The DNP author, nurse manager, and nurse lead of the outpatient surgery department conducted a daily leadership observation audit. The audits concluded on September 1, 2017.

The Study stage commenced one month after the checklist was piloted (September 1, 2017) and all necessary revisions had been made. The results from the first month of the checklist implementation were analyzed and evaluated during the second month of the pilot study. An executive summary of the audit findings was written during the study phase. A paper and pencil survey was distributed on September 5, 2017 to the pre-operative and intra-operative nurses to elicit their perceptions about the effectiveness of the hand-off process using the checklist and the ease of its use. Nurses were asked to complete the survey and return it to the DNP author by September 12, 2017.

In the Act stage, the first 31 days of the project findings were presented to the stakeholders to determine whether to continue or terminate the project (September 19, 2017). Once the stakeholders decided to continue the project, steps were developed to improve and standardize the proposed changes as indicated from the Study phase. Preparation for the next steps to further implement the project involved planning a subsequent PDSA cycle for the inpatient operative setting.

Model for Improvement

Figure 1. PDSA cycle. The Model for Improvement was developed by Associates in Process Improvement. Accessed on the Institute for Healthcare Improvement website at: <http://www.ihi.org/resources/Pages/HowtoImprove/default.aspx>. Reprinted with permission.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A review of literature was conducted to gather information regarding the hand off process and the role of communication in preventing adverse events in the peri-operative setting. The electronic data bases used were PubMed, Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), Cochrane Library, and Google Scholar. The search was limited to peer-reviewed articles written in English and conducted from 2008 to present. The following keywords were used to search for articles: transition of care, hand off, checklist, shift report, ineffective communication, reduction of errors, teamwork, and perioperative environment. The articles selected were systematic reviews, meta-analysis, qualitative, and quantitative research investigations. The articles were reviewed and the selection was based on title, relevance to the purpose of the project, and pertinence to the peri-operative environment. This literature review focused on the following topics: overview of communication breakdown, clinicians' perceptions of checklists, effects of checklists in transition of care, and design and implementation of checklists.

Overview of Communication Breakdown

Hospitals are high-risk environments in which 10% of inpatients suffer from preventable adverse events (Patel et al., 2014). Surgical procedures pose considerable risks for complications resulting from poor communication during hand off to the next level of care. These complications result in the compromise of patient safety (Patel et al., 2014). A study conducted by Ong and Loirera (2011) concluded that communication failures were equally distributed in all phases of surgical care: pre-operative (38%), intra-operative (30%), and post-operative (32%). The same study revealed that handoffs and

transfers in care were associated with communication breakdowns that lead to patient complications with a 43% error incidence rate (Ong & Loirera, 2011).

To improve patient outcomes, hospitals in different settings have adopted and implemented checklist tools to be used during the hand off process (Treadwell, Lucas, & Tsou, 2013). Clinical hand off is an established method for the transference of responsibility and accountability for patient care from one clinical staff member to another staff member (Jeff et al., 2013; Johnson & Cowin, 2013). The process involves the transference of essential patient information (Jeff et al., 2013; Johnson & Cowin, 2013). The hand off provides the receiving clinicians with an opportunity to interact, ask and clarify questions, involve the patient if capable, and validate the status of the patient with the sending clinicians (Jeffs et al., 2013). Clinical hand off is critical for continuity of care, quality, and the safety of the patient (Johnson & Cowin, 2013; Salzwedel et al., 2013).

Information about physiologic monitoring devices (invasive lines, transducers, transport monitors, etc.) are additional sources of information that need to be discussed during the transference of information (Petrovic et al., 2015). As technology advances, so does the complexity and potential for errors within the surgical environment (McElroy et al., 2015). With 275,000 surgical procedures being performed daily across the nation, there is heightened awareness for leaders of the medical community to improve surgical patient safety (Lyons & Popejoy, 2014; Verdaasdonk, Stassen, Widhiasmara, & Dankelman, 2009).

Due to positive research outcomes, checklists are being adopted in various clinical settings. Although there are positive findings, further studies were recommended to

validate the degree of effectiveness in improving clinical outcomes. Areas of suggested research include investigations of the effectiveness of checklists in different clinical settings, the efficacy of the checklists in exploring key safety issues, and exploration for improvement of compliance with the use of checklists (Johnson & Cowin, 2013; Lingard et al., 2008; Lyons & Popejoy, 2014; Treadwell, Lucas, & Tsou, 2013; Verdaasdonk et al., 2009). In addition, Verdaasdonk et al. (2009) recommended a need to identify checklists for specific settings.

Ong and Coirera (2011) concluded that contributing factors for failure of effective hand offs are poor communication, lack of established consistent policies, variability of staff communication, unstructured hand off, and informational redundancy. Institutional culture and inter-departmental relationships are also factors that impact the effectiveness of checklist implementation (Haynes et al., 2009; McElroy et al., 2015; Robins & Dai, 2015).

Clinicians' Perceptions of Checklists

Clinicians must perceive that a change in practice truly influences patient outcomes in order to ensure widespread adoption of a new practice. In a study conducted by Johnson and Cowin (2013), a group of nurses identified positive outcomes when using hand offs and proposed areas for improvement of the hand off process. Their feedback noted that staff communications improved, patient participation increased, and patient-centered care was promoted.

In the quick pace of the surgical environment, staff recognized that in their efforts to expedite efficient care, they may fail to document critical information (Johnson & Cowin, 2013). Failure to document critical information in the medical record may result

in an adverse event. However, at times this information may be captured during the verbal hand off process (Johnson & Cowin, 2013). In studies by Jeffs et al. (2013) and Johnson and Cowin (2013) they concluded that stronger communication resulted in positive patient care outcomes and efficiency in the gathering of critical information.

Lingard et al. (2008) reported that staff noticed improvements in teamwork and team communication with the implementation of the hand off checklist. The improvements in teamwork were attributed to a reduction in communication failures and promotion in proactive and collaborative communication among team members (Lingard et al., 2008). In a similar study, nurses noted that a checklist improved accountability and efficiency (Jeffs et al., 2013). In the same study, nurses indicated that the checklist provided them an initial contact with their patient, which enabled them to conduct quick assessments and prioritize tasks (Jeffs et al., 2013).

Johnson and Cowin (2013) discovered that nurses perceived the lack of communication standardization contributed to confusion and inaccuracy during the hand off process. Areas of proposed improvements were the timing and location of hand offs (Johnson & Cowin, 2013). It was also recommended in the study of Johnson and Cowin (2013) that a location for the hand off process should be established within each department. Furthermore, they concluded that the discipline of a standardized process enables the staff to provide accurate and concise information in a timely manner.

Effects of Checklists in Transition of Care

Many studies have shown that checklist tools are associated with significant improvement in providing safe quality patient care. Healthcare organizations continue to explore the benefits of the checklist tool for implementation. Haynes et al. (2009)

conducted a global study of a 19-item surgical checklist based on the WHO Guidelines and Recommendations for Surgical Patient Safety. The outcomes of the study favored the use of a checklist, and complication and morbidity rates decreased from 11% to 7% and 1.5% to 0.8% respectively. Similar studies in different settings (Operating Room to Intensive Care Unit, Operating Room to Post Anesthesia Care Unit) showed a decrease in mortality and morbidity and demonstrated improved teamwork and communication (Lyons & Popejoy, 2014; Patel et al., 2014; Petrovec et al., 2015; Robins & Dai, 2015; Salzwedel, Mai, Punke, Kluge, & Reuter, 2016; Salzwedel et al., 2013). In addition, there were improvements in the quality of care delivered related to the increase in the quality and quantity of shared information (Salzwedel et al., 2016).

Moreover, malpractice claims may be reduced through the use of a structured communication process and improved patient care outcomes. Patel et al. (2014) found that adoption of a checklist in the pre-operative and intra-operative areas could prevent or reduce the incidence of negative events including wrong-site surgery, medication errors, failure of laboratory tests to be drawn, failure to follow up on ordered diagnostic tests, and incorrect consents.

The studies of Petrovic et al. (2015) and Verdaasdonk et al. (2009) suggest that the process of using a checklist strengthens the nursing workforce. Their studies showed that nurse turnover decreased by 16% and employee satisfaction increased by 19% after the implementation of a checklist. In addition, safety in the workplace increased from good to outstanding (Petrovic et al., 2015; Verdaasdonk et al., 2009). Malekzadeh, Mazluom, Etezadi, and Tasserri (2013) and Verdaasdonk et al. (2009) also concluded that the use of a checklist improves standardization of clinical performance, improves nurses'

practice, and ensures that protocols are consistently and correctly followed. The use of a checklist as a guide for communication prevents the reliance on memory and potential failed communication (Verdaasdonk et al., 2009).

The usage of a checklist during the hand off process also supports team engagement. The actual presence of team members during the transition of care promotes team building and camaraderie (Lingard et al., 2008; Petrovic et al., 2015; Verdaasdonk et al., 2009). Moreover, communication styles among clinicians affect the quality of the hand off (Robins & Dai, 2015). The tone, volume, and speed of the delivery of information impact the handoff process between caregivers (Robins & Dai, 2015). Moreover, checklists mitigate variances in clinical practice, which arise from unique clinician attributes.

Haynes et al. (2009) noted in their study that in order for the hand off process to be effective, it requires cultural, behavioral, and practice changes among members of the involved departments. Increased productivity, time constraints, clinical workloads, and fast turnovers may limit the clinicians' ability to focus on the process (Gillespie, Chaboyer, Longbottom, & Wallis, 2010; Robins & Dai, 2015). Nonetheless, several studies showed that the use of the checklist during the hand off did not add extra time to the process (Robins & Dain, 2015; Salzwedel et al., 2016; Salzwedel et al., 2013).

Design and Implementation of Checklists

Several studies identified methods for designing and implementing a checklist. The success of a research project is enhanced when the design for implementation is structured, planned, and has the collaboration of the stakeholders. Education (staff understanding), identification of a project leader, staff involvement, management

involvement, flexibility for modification of the checklist, and timeliness of feedback were the principal contributors linked to positive outcomes (Gillespie et al., 2010; Petrovic et al., 2015; Treadwell, Lucas, & Tsou, 2012). Successful implementation of the checklist is dependent upon organizational and cultural factors and helps to define roles and responsibilities of team members (Verdaasdonk et al., 2009). A strategy for change of the checklist design, use, and assessment should be revised with team involvement (Verdaasdonk et al., 2009). This will encourage team acceptance, ownership, and enable them to create a feedback loop to reassess and evaluate the tool for ongoing improvement (Verdaasdonk et al., 2009).

A systematic review conducted by Patel et al. (2014) demonstrated a need for the checklist tool to be concise, simple, user-friendly, and have an emphasis on critical information in order to be adoptable and effective. The omission of these criteria could lead to negative patient outcomes (Patel et al., 2014). Modification of a checklist that is not tailored to a specific setting was identified as a top barrier for checklist implementation. Other barriers include staff resistance to adoption of the checklist into their job duties, skepticism towards change in workflow, and negative attitudes of participating clinicians (Patel et al., 2014). Another barrier to be considered is the perception of increased financial impact during implementation. Cost during implementation is associated with the development, modification, and training of staff (Treadwell, Lucas, & Tsou, 2012).

The studies conducted by Patel et al. (2014) and Salzwedel et al. (2013) discussed the need for additional training and research to establish consistency of the hand off practice. In addition, Patel et al. (2014) recommended having booster training sessions

after implementation of the checklist. This supplemental training allows for an opportunity to reassess the process and receive feedback from the end users (Patel et al., 2014).

Conclusions

The adoption of checklists has resulted in significant improvements in patient care outcomes (Lingard et al., 2008; Lyons & Popejoy, 2014; Patel et al., 2014; Salzwedel et al., 2016; Treadwell, Lucas, & Tsou, 2012; Verdaasdonk et al., 2009). Despite the increased adoption of checklists, The Joint Commission (TJC) estimates 80% of medical errors are due to communication breakdowns (Robins & Dai, 2015). Further studies are required to maximize the potential for usage and acceptance of the checklist tool (Lyons & Popejoy, 2014).

Continued development of identified opportunities should be a top priority of medical and nursing leaders. In an effort for leaders to improve communication and the quality of patient care, standardized communication processes are being developed, implemented, and evaluated for adoption in different patient care areas. Medical and nursing leaders recognize the need to support research surrounding improving communication in the workplace. This quality improvement project was implemented to bridge the gap of communication breakdowns during the transition of care in the perioperative setting of the DNP author's workplace.

METHODS

The method section of this paper describes the project's design, setting, sample, ethical issues, measures, and data collection procedures as well as the intervention and evaluation plan for this Quality Improvement (QI) project. The focus of this QI project was to develop, implement, and evaluate a hand off tool that would serve as a checklist for the pre-operative and intra-operative nurses to use during the transition of patients from one surgical care area to the next.

Project Design

This was an EBP, QI project with a three-part design that included a pre and post data collection of communication errors (Figure 2). The first part began with pre-data collection of errors identified in occurrence reports from May 1, 2016 to July 31, 2017. This review included examining communication errors that occurred in the outpatient surgery department of the project hospital. An occurrence report, as defined by the project hospital, is a documented event that occurred outside the normal process of care and is reported by anyone employed by the pilot hospital. The events of interest are related to communication breakdown in the pre-operative area. The second part involved the development of the Pre-Operative Checklist Tool (POCT) and the establishment of its content validity through a review by an expert panel (i.e. the hospital's Surgery Safety Committee). Nurses were then educated on the use of the checklist tool prior to its implementation. The third part included the evaluation of the reliability, effectiveness, compliance, and ease of use of the POCT. In addition, an analysis was conducted comparing the rate of communication errors in the pre-operative and intra-operative settings during specified timeframes pre and post implementation of the checklist.

The POCT was developed during a three-month timeframe from May 1, 2017 to July 31, 2017 and implemented from August 1, 2017 to September 30, 2017. The checklist was created by the DNP author in collaboration with the nurse manager and nurse lead of the outpatient surgery department. The structure of the POCT and the specific content items included were based upon the Universal Protocol Checklist Recommendations described by TJC (TJC, 2017). The focus of the POCT (modified from that of the Universal Protocol) included patient identification, wrong site surgery, and safety requirements for the pre-operative area. The Surgery Safety Committee reviewed and approved the POCT. Once approved, education was provided to the pre-operative and intra-operative nurses regarding the POCT, the hand off process, and audit processes (see intervention section for description of educational plan). The nurses who worked from 7:00 AM to 3:00 PM received education during their mandatory July staff meeting.

The first month of the pilot project (August 1, 2017 to August 31, 2017) focused on the implementation of the POCT. Issues and barriers related to effective implementation of the checklist tool were identified. From September 1 to September 30, 2017, the nurses were required to continue the use the POCT to maintain continuity of the process until the evaluations and recommendations from the stakeholders occurred. No data collection or audits were completed during this time. This project was conducted in collaboration with the outpatient leadership team, staff, and Risk Department. The evaluation of the tool focused on compliance, reliability, effectiveness, and checklist ease of use during the pre-operative to intra-operative phases of patient care.

QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT TIMELINE
PERI-OPERATIVE HAND OFF: A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

Pre-work	May 1, 2017 July 31, 2017	August 1, 2017 September 30, 2017 (Implementation phase)	September 5, 2017 September 12, 2017 (Evaluation phase)	September 1, 2017 December 31, 2017 (Evaluation phase)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Pre-data collection of the occurrence reports related to communication errors from the outpatient surgery department of the pilot hospital from May 1, 2016 to 31, 2016. -Staff approval. -Pilot hospital approval to conduct project and collection of occurrence report. -Pilot hospital IRB designation. -CSULB IRB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Development of the Pre-operative Checklist tool (POCT). -POCT approval from the Surgery Safety Committee expert panels. -Pre-operative and intra-operative nurses education by the DNP author regarding hand off process, structured hand off, validity of the POCT, timeline, stakeholders, purpose, audit processes, and survey. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation phase of the study. -Data collection through the POCT daily audits and daily leadership observations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Nurses' perceptions survey were conducted. Nurses who were involved during the implementation phase were asked to complete a 6 – question pencil and paper survey (5 Likert Scale and 2 narratives). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Continue to use the POCT to maintain continuity of the process. -No data collection during this time. -Evaluation of the POCT for reliability, effectiveness, compliance and ease of use. -Comparison of the pre-tool data and post tool data on communication errors.

Figure 2. Summary of project timeline.

Setting

The QI project took place in the outpatient surgery department at a community hospital in San Diego County. The surgery outpatient area has four operating rooms and performs an average of 250 surgeries per month. There are five-admission/ interview rooms designated for the pre-operative assessment of patients. The recovery area consists of 10 bay areas. The department is open Monday through Friday from 5:30 AM until the last patient is discharged from the recovery area, typically around 9:00 PM. The procedures performed involved many specialty areas: orthopedic, gynecologic, podiatry, general, eyes/ ears/ nose (ENT), and plastics, reconstructive, genitourinary, and dental. The surgery population includes adolescents age 12 to 18 and adults 18 and over.

The surgery outpatient department employs 29 nurses with varying levels of surgical experience (pre-operative, intra-operative, and post-operative). The nurses work eight-hour shifts. There are two nurses assigned to the pre-operative area for admitting and conducting patient assessments throughout the day. There is one nurse assigned to each patient in the intra-operative area. Ninety percent of the nurses hold a bachelor's degree in nursing.

The project hospital has been designated as a Magnet hospital for the past 12 years. The leadership and staff are committed to ongoing development of nursing practice and process improvement. The majority of the nurses in the outpatient surgery department have worked for the project hospital for more than 20 years.

Sample

Inclusion criteria for sampling of individual patient data and recording of relevant patient information on the POCT included only elective patient surgical cases scheduled

from 7:15 AM to 3:00 PM, Monday through Friday from August 1, 2017 to August 31, 2017. Elective cases scheduled from 3:00 PM or later as well as any cases added to the surgical schedule the same day the surgery was to take place without prior scheduling were excluded from the data collection. The average total monthly caseload in the surgery outpatient department was approximately 250 surgeries.

Twenty-nine nurses were employed in the surgery outpatient department at the time of the study. Approximately 20 of the 29 nurses worked in the pre-operative and intra-operative areas between the hours of 7:00 AM and 3:00 PM. These were the nurses who were asked to complete the Nurses' Perceptions Survey Tool (NPST) following the first month of the implementation of the POCT (August 1, 2017 to August 31, 2017).

Ethical Issues

The Surgery Safety Committee and Surgery Operations Committee of the project hospital reviewed this QI project and gave written confirmations of approval (Appendices A and B). The Surgery Safety Committee is comprised of the surgical leadership team, the Medical Director, Risk Department, and other departments on an as needed basis. This committee meets once a week to review critical events that occurred in the surgical services department. This committee is responsible for developing action plans to remediate anticipated negative events. The Surgery Operations Committee is comprised of the surgery leadership team, the Medical Director, and the Chief of Surgery. This committee meets once a month to discuss operational workflow issues for surgical services. The Vice President/ Chief Nurse Operation Executive of the project hospital provided written approval to conduct this project at the outpatient surgery department (Appendix C). The leadership team and staff of the outpatient surgery department were

informed of the project during their one-hour staff meeting and endorsed this QI project on March 21, 2017. The project was submitted for approval to the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the project hospital. On April 18, 2017, it was determined to be and approved as a QI project (Appendix D). This QI project was also submitted to IRB of California State University, Long Beach. It was reviewed and approved on July 3, 2017 (Appendix E).

The project hospital routinely collects occurrence event data. The DNP author was granted permission to use de-identified data identified in reports collected from the hospital's occurrence reporting system. Preventing communication breakdowns occurring in the pre-operative and intra-operative areas was the sole focus for this project. Thus, comparison of the pre and post intervention data was of interest to the author. The post data collection process (conducted after the one-month implementation) was similar to the pre-data collection process, which did not include patient identification. The pre-data occurrence reports were captured and errors categorized as associated with communication breakdowns were extracted. The Surgery Safety Committee approved the DNP author to access the occurrence reporting system

Data Collection/Measures

A pre-operative checklist was developed and implemented as a tool to improve communication during transitions of care for the pre-operative and intra-operative areas. In addition, the daily POCT audits and daily leadership observations by the DNP author, the nurse manager, and the nurse lead of the outpatient surgery department were conducted. This was to validate reliability, effectiveness, and compliance of the POCT and the hand off process (August 1, 2017 to August 31, 2017). The nurses' perceptions

and ease of use of the POCT was evaluated through the use of the NPST after one month of implementation (September 5, 2017 to September 12, 2017). The NPST (Appendix F) and the daily POCT audit (Appendix H) were developed in collaboration with the nurse manager and the nurse lead of the outpatient surgery department. The DNP author met with the nurse manager and nurse lead to design the daily pre-operative checklist audit tool and the NPST. These tools were derived from prior experience and knowledge of the DNP author, the nurse manager, and the nurse lead, which was gleaned from working on prior QI projects. Reported documented clinical events that occurred during the first month of the pilot project (August 1, 2017 to August 31, 2017) were collected and compared to the pre collection data collected from August 1, 2016 to August 31, 2016.

Daily Pre-Operative Checklist Audit Tool

This entailed tallying the number of elective cases scheduled from 7:15 AM to 3:00 PM. It included the number of completed (all components of the checklist were checked off) documented checklist tools, number of incomplete documented checklist tools, and negative clinical events that were documented through the occurrence reporting system during the first month of the pilot project.

At the end of each workday, the nurse manager collected the checklist tools at the predetermined secured designated location. The nurse manager then counted the number of cases performed from 7:15 AM to 3:00 PM, reviewed the checklist tools for accuracy, and tallied the results on the daily audit tool. The nurse manager of the surgery outpatient department secured the audit tools in a locked area in her office. The DNP author and the nurse manager met every day for 15 minutes to review checklists and assure questions and issues of staff were addressed on a timely manner.

Daily Leadership Observation Audit

The observation audit involved verification that the checklist tool was in its designated location (on top of the chart), two nurses (one pre-operative and one intra-operative) conducted the structured hand off process, the checklist components were addressed, and the checklist tool was signed off by the two nurses conducting the hand off process.

The DNP candidate, the nurse manager, and the nurse lead of the outpatient surgery department conducted the daily leadership observation audits. Each person was expected to observe one random hand off process per day. An observation audit tool was utilized for each observation (Appendix G). Observers tallied their observations on the daily leadership observation tally tool (Appendix I). The pre-operative and intra-operative nurses were blinded to the daily leadership observation audits. The DNP author, nurse manager, and nurse lead scheduled a weekly meeting for 30 minutes to assure consistency was maintained regarding the observation process and review the status of the project. This allowed the DNP author to connect and establish support for the team.

Nurses' Perceptions Survey Tool

After completion of the one-month pilot project (September 5, 2017 to September 12, 2017), the participating nurses were asked to complete a seven-question paper and pencil survey (five questions using a Likert Scale and two narratives).

The nurses were not required to provide any self-identifying information when completing the survey. Nurses were asked to leave the completed survey tool in a locked drop box located outside of the manager's office.

Intervention

There was no structured hand off process in place in the perioperative areas of the outpatient and inpatient location of the project hospital. The goal was to use EBP to alleviate potential errors (medication errors, failure to follow up on laboratory and diagnostic test results). The potential for errors and lack of structure caused physicians' to voice dissatisfaction due to delay of cases. Therefore, the DNP author implemented a structured hand off process using a checklist tool.

The DNP author, the nurse manager, and the nurse lead met three times for two hours to develop the POCT. The first meeting occurred on June 27, 2017 and involved a review of the Universal Protocol from the Joint Commission, 2017 and identification of components needed for the checklist. The components included safety requirements needed for the patient or family members to validate prior to surgery. The DNP author formatted the POCT before the second meeting. A sample of the POCT, drafted by the DNP author, was provided as a guide for development (Appendix K). The second meeting (July 5, 2017) entailed a review of the checklist content and format and the establishment of consensus that the checklist was a reliable and valid tool and was ready to be sent to the next level for final approval. The third meeting occurred on July 11, 2017 with the Surgery Safety Committee experts for final approval.

Staff education took place on July 18, 2017 prior to piloting the project and included information about the background and the validity of the tool, the purpose of the project, timeline, stakeholders, and the hand off process (Appendix J). In addition, an overview of the audits and survey were presented during the education meeting.

The checklist tool was included as part of the perioperative packet and was clipped on top of each patient chart. The hand off process required two nurses, one nurse from the pre-operative area and one nurse from the intra-operative area. Both nurses were required to verbally address all components of the checklist tool. Each component was marked with a check mark to reflect that all criteria had been addressed. At the end of the hand off process, both nurses were required to sign off on the checklist. An area was provided in a secured location for the nurses to submit the signed off checklists. The intra-operative nurses submitted the checklist tools prior to transporting patients to the intra-operative phase. The nurse manager collected the completed checklists at the end of the day for the daily audits.

RESULTS

The results section discusses the analysis and the findings of this quality improvement project designed to address implementation of the pre-operative checklist. The DNP author's goal was to improve quality, safety, efficiency, and patient and physician satisfaction through the use of a pre-operative checklist. The author utilized various data points for the pilot study. The findings of the study are as follows:

Daily Pre-Operative Audit Checklist

The timeframe for the pre-operative checklist data collection took place from August 1, 2017 through August 31, 2017 (Appendix H). During that time frame, a total of 299 cases were scheduled at the pilot site from 7 am to 3 pm, Monday through Friday. The pre-operative checklist was used in all 299 cases and 270 of the checklists had all items correctly completed for a 90% accuracy rate. The author reviewed the 29 incomplete checklists and found no trends related to specific unmarked items.

Daily Leadership Observation Audit

The designated leaders responsible for the daily observational audits collected data on four compliance issues that were to take place during the pre-operative transitional handoff of information from nurses working in the pre-operative awaiting area to the operating room nurses (Appendix I). First, there was 100% (65/65) nurse to nurse hand off compliance (i.e., there was active sharing of patient information between the two nurses). Second, the checklist tool was placed at the designated location (placed in front of each patient's chart) 100% (65/65) of the time. Third, 95% (62/65) of the checklist components were correctly addressed/checked. Fourth, both groups of nurses signed off on the checklist 100% (65/65) of the time.

Nurses' Perceptions Survey

The survey was conducted beginning September 5, 2017 through September 12, 2017. There were 20 nurse participants involved during the pilot study. Eighteen nurses (90%) submitted completed survey materials and two did not return their surveys. The survey had five questions using a Likert-scale response for participants to indicate their level of agreement. Participants were also given two additional questions which asked them to comment, provide suggestions, recommendations, and feedback on anything that they believed would improve the checklist. The questions and comments were as follows:

1) *The checklist identified the critical safety components for the transition of care*

Seventeen nurses responded to this question. There were eight (47%) who strongly agreed, five (29%) who agreed, three (18%) were neutral, and one (6%) disagreed (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Question one response.

2) The checklist tool is easy to use

Eighteen nurses responded to this question. Five (28%) strongly agreed, two (11%) agreed, one (6%) was neutral, six (33%) disagreed, and four (22%) strongly disagreed (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Question two response.

3) The checklist tool will improve communication between the pre-operative and intra-operative areas

There were eighteen responses to this question. Seven (39%) strongly agreed, seven (39%) agreed, one (5%) was neutral, and three (17%) disagreed (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Question three response.

4) I am likely to recommend the checklist tool for implementation

Eighteen responded to this question. Six (33%) strongly agreed, two (11%) agreed, one (6%) was neutral, six (33%) disagreed, and three (17%) strongly disagreed (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Question four response.

5) The time added by using the structured hand off checklist was valuable

Eighteen responded to this question. Six (33%) strongly agreed, two (11%) agreed, four (22%) responded neutrally, two (11%) disagreed, and four (22%) strongly disagreed (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Question five response.

6) Aside from patient identification, allergies, procedure, site/side, laboratory, and diagnostic tests verifications, do you have recommendations for item (s) that should be added to and/or deleted from the checklist tool?

One nurse suggested to add “limb alert.” Three noted that the items on the checklist were excessive to review. One nurse mentioned that the checklist slowed down the pre-op assessment, especially for the first cases of the day. Another nurse noted that the checklist was hard to follow. And there was one recommendation to add “N/A” as an option.

In summary (Figure 8), the response to question one (the checklist identified the critical safety components for the transition of care) was most favorable and supported the goal assumption of this project. The pre-operative checklist positively assisted in identifying safety critical components prior to taking patients to the operating room. Next, the nurses' responses to question three (the checklist tool will improve communication between the pre-operative and intra-operative areas) substantiated that improved communication occurred through the use of the pre-operative checklist. Although responses to question four (I am likely to recommend the checklist tool for implementation) and question five (the time added by using the structured hand off checklist was valuable) scored between neutral and agreed, the results indicated the nurses were likely to recommend the pre-operative checklist for implementation and the hand off process, regardless of the increased time for pre-operative assessment. Question two (the checklist tool is easy to use) divulged a need for the checklist to be revised for implementation. Figure 8 summarizes the mean score of each of the five questions.

Figure 8. Survey response averages

7) Please list any suggestions or feedback

Nine of the nurses surveyed noted that the checklist should be arranged to follow the order of the chart. Three stated that finding another nurse to partner with to do the checklist slowed the pre-operative assessment process down. One nurse suggested providing education surrounding how to fill out the pre-operative checklist form. Three felt that there were too many items on the checklist.

One nurse indicated the checklist “must be adopted for implementation.” One nurse added personal support stating that, “it is a great tool.” Another nurse wrote “having two nurses during transition of care” is a huge benefit.”

Clinical Events Related to Pre-Operative Assessment

The pilot hospital's occurrence reporting system was used as one of the data points to measure the effectiveness of the implementation of the pre-operative checklist. The purpose of using this information was to determine whether there was a positive or negative clinical impact on patient outcomes by using the tool. The reported clinical events from May to December of 2016 were compared to those that occurred in the timeframe of May to December of 2017 (Figure 9).

In May 2016, two clinical events were reported. These were missed medication in the pre-operative area and incorrect consent. In the following month (June, 2016), three clinical events were reported. Two were missed medication in the pre-operative area and missing required documentation (patient's history and physical from the surgeon). During July 2016, two clinical events were generated. One was a missing consent and the second involved missed medication in the pre-operative area. In August 2016, two clinical events were reported related to communication breakdowns in the pre-operative area. These incidences involved missed pre-op medication and a failure to recognize and implement isolation precautions. There were also two pre-operative events reported in September 2016. They included missed laboratory orders and a missed consent. In October of 2016, two clinical events were reported. One was for a missed consent and the other was an incomplete consent. For November 2016, three clinical events were reported. Two were for missed pre-op medications and one was for an incorrect consent. December of 2016, there were no occurrences reported.

In the months prior to the pilot study, there were reported clinical events. During May of 2017, there were two clinical events both related to incomplete consents. In June

of 2017, there was one event related to a missed pre-op medication. In July of 2017, there were two clinical events reported. One resulted from a missed laboratory test. The other was due to incomplete paper requirement. During the first month of the pilot study (August, 2017), there were no negative clinical events reported. The month of September of 2017 also ended without any reported negative clinical events. In October of 2017, there were no negative clinical events reported as well. In November 2017, there were zero occurrences. However, two cases were appropriately cancelled in the pre-operative area when problems were identified through the hand off process. In December of 2017, no reported occurrences.

Discussion and Dissemination

Seventy-six percent of the nurses' surveyed identified that the checklist contained appropriate safety components for pre-operative assessments. Fifty-five percent of the nurses did not find the checklist tool easy to use. This was a consistent comment from just over half of the nurses who participated in the pilot. Seventy seven percent of the participants believed that the pre-operative checklist tool would improve communication. Fifty percent did not recommend the pre-operative checklist for implementation.

The DNP candidate had several meetings with nurses from the pre-operative and intra-operative areas for the purpose of gaining a better understanding of the survey results. The nurses' main reason for not wanting to recommend adoption of the checklist was related to the organization of the checklist. The nurses strongly recommended that the criteria be listed and arranged based on the order that the items appeared in the patient's chart. The nurses believed that using the chart organization would prevent them from having to flip back and forth searching for the checklist item within the chart, wasting valuable time. Nurses believed the process of going back and forth through the

chart increased the time it took to transition a patient from the pre-operative nurse to the intra-operative nurse. However, fifty percent agreed that the time spent using the checklist was valuable, 25% were neutral, and 25%, disagreed.

Figure 9. Clinical Events Reported Comparison (May-December 2016 and 2017).

During the daily audit, the DNP candidate frequently connected with the charge nurses and physicians to capture any missed or undocumented issues encountered by the staff. There were no reported issues during the two-month pilot study.

The DNP candidate gathered a workgroup of ten nurses from the pre-operative and intra operative areas who volunteered to assist in revising the pre-operative checklist tool. The workgroup met multiple times from mid-September to mid-October to revise the pre-operative checklist for content and organization. The revised checklist was presented during daily reports to all staff for discussion, consensus, and approval of the final checklist (October 12, 2017). On October 16, 2017, the revised preoperative checklist was implemented.

Clinical Implications

The results of this quality improvement pilot study validated the benefits of EBP guiding nursing care. The framework of EBP served as the foundation upon which this DNP project was designed to create a checklist that would provide structure, safety, and accuracy during the pre-operative assessment phase. The results of the clinical events reported during the pilot phase were compared to those of May and December of 2016. There were no negative events that occurred from the time the checklist was first initiated August 1, 2017 until December 31, 2017 when the pilot project data collection was completed. The pre-operative and intra-operative nurses at the pilot hospital agreed with the revisions and adopted the revised checklist on October 16, 2017 (Appendix L). The revised checklist provided nurses with a tool and a process which is now being used in every pre-operative assessment.

After the October 16, 2017, revised pre-operative checklist was adopted. The author continued to evaluate the tool's use for 90 days ending on January 16, 2018. The

90-day review consisted of the DNP author monitoring the staff's use of the revised pre-operative checklist by rounding and requesting staff feedback. The DNP author attended the February 6, 2018 staff meeting to finalize the project and provided updates to the staff. In addition, the DNP author also presented the project and findings to the Surgical Safety Quality Committee which was attended by the Surgery Medical Director, representatives from Quality and Risk Management, and the Surgical Services Leadership team. The presentation was well received by the committee.

There are plans in place to extend this QI project to the inpatient surgical area. Due to the implementation of another major project in the pilot hospital, its implementation was delayed to May 2018. The author intends to use the same framework (PDSA) to design a checklist that best meets the needs of the staff working in the inpatient surgical area.

Lesson Gleaned from the Study

In reflection, the DNP author learned that collaboration with clinical experts empowers staff to make decisions, engage, support, and buy into a practice change. The importance of this factor cannot be underestimated. It is imperative to understand the thought processes and issues facing stakeholders. In order for staff to be invested and instrumental in quality improvement projects affecting their daily workflow, they need to be involved in the decision making process. This helps to support implementation of any project with the other nurses when they see the clinical experts of the department driving the initiative.

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APPENDIX A**LETTER FROM SURGERY OPERATIONS COMMITTEE**

March 4, 2017

To whom it may concern:

I am writing this letter to express my unreserved support for my colleague Bernadette Roberson's project: "Perioperative Handoff: A Quality improvement project."

As OR Medical Director at for the last 10 years, it has been my pleasure to work with Bernie in her roles as clinical lead and later as Administrative Director for Surgical Services. She is a person who not only has good ideas and a good heart, but she also has the drive, tenacity, and personal skills to see her projects to a successful conclusion. I am thankful to have had the opportunity to work with her.

Please feel free to contact me if I might be of any further assistance.

Sincerely,

OR Medical Director,

APPENDIX B**LETTER FROM SURGERY SAFETY COMMITTEE**

March 4, 2017

To whom it may concern:

This letter is to acknowledge Bernadette Roberson's DNP project regarding perioperative handoff for implementation and evaluation. The Operating Room Safety Committee supports this project.

Sincerely,

*Clinical Risk Specialist
Operating Room Safety Committee Meeting Facilitator*

APPENDIX C

LETTER FROM THE VICE PRESIDENT/CHIEF NURSE EXECUTIVE

800 N State College Blvd.
Fullerton, Ca. 92831

April 4, 2017

Dear [REDACTED],

I am currently enrolled in the Doctorate of Practice in Nursing (DNP) program at California State University (CSU) Fullerton. One of the requirements for graduation is to develop a project in my respective clinical setting. This project needs to be evidence based. In evaluating my areas, I have identified the need to improve communication in the perioperative areas. The title of my project is, "Perioperative Handover: A quality improvement project."

This project will involve:

- 1) Data collection of occurrences related to communication-based errors identified in the pre-operative area. The data will be collected from the communication sections of our MIDAS occurrence reporting system. The primary focus will be on cases that involve communication breakdowns with actual and potential safety issues in the perioperative setting.
- 2) Collaboration with the leadership team, staff, and the Medical Director of the outpatient setting in order to develop a hand off tool. A workgroup will be formed and include members from the preoperative and intraoperative areas to formulate a check off list. The list will encompass the preoperative surgery safety requirements. The hand off tool will be piloted for a one month period by the preoperative and intraoperative nurses. This will serve as a checklist during their preoperative assessment.
- 3) The checklist will be evaluated for effectiveness and nurses perceptions for ease of use through a survey.
- 4) After completion of the pilot study, data will be trended regarding nurse's perceptions and satisfaction related to use of the checklist tool. All clinical outcomes during the study period will be analyzed and trended.

I understand the need for protection of patient information. The data I intend to collect (pre-post) for this project will be de-identified to comply with Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) regulations. This quality improvement project will also be reviewed and evaluated for approval by the California State University Long Beach Institutional Review Board (IRB).

██████████
April 4, 2017

Page 2

Throughout the course of the project, the project materials will be protected and reviewed by the project chairs (Dr. Margaret Brady and Dr. Melissa Dyo) and myself.

This project is supported by our Surgery Safety Committee and the Surgery Operations Committee. Attached are the letters of support from the two committees.

Once the project has been completed, this will be presented to the DNP committee, and Surgery Supervisory Committee.

I am asking for your approval as the Chief Nursing and Operations Executive (CNOE) of ██████████ to conduct my perioperative handover, quality improvement project in the outpatient setting of the hospital.

Thank you,

Bernadette Roberson, RN, MSN, CNOR
DNP Candidate
CSU Fullerton

Approved: ██████████
██████████

Vice President/Chief Nursing and Operations Executive

APPENDIX D

IRB APPROVAL FROM PILOT HOSPITAL

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED] **Office for the Protection of Research Subjects**

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

April 18, 2017

TO: Bernadette Roberson

RE: QA Project using nursing checklist

The [REDACTED] previewed your proposal and determined that it does not meet criteria as human subjects research. You will not need to submit this Quality Improvement proposal to the IRB.

Sincerely,

[REDACTED]

APPENDIX E

IRB APPROVAL FROM CSU, LONG BEACH

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH

OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS

DATE: July 3, 2017

TO: Bernadette Roberson

FROM: CSULB IRB

PROJECT TITLE: [1092089-1] Perioperative Handoff: A Quality Improvement Project

REFERENCE #: 17-407

SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

ACTION: EXEMPT

EFFECTIVE DATE: July 3, 2017

Thank you for submitting the New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board has ACKNOWLEDGED your submission. No further action on submission 1092089-1 is required at this time.

The following items are acknowledged in this submission:

- Application Form - Bernadette CSULB IRB Application-F.doc (UPDATED: 06/29/2017)
- Letter - Faculty Advisor Letter.docx (UPDATED: 06/23/2017)
- Other - Roberson, B. - Appendix - with Rotation.pdf (UPDATED: 06/23/2017)

Based on 45 CFR 46.101(b)(1) this project qualifies for IRB Exemption.

If you have any questions, please contact the IRB Office at IRB@csulb.edu. Please include your project title and reference number in all correspondence with this committee.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board's records.

APPENDIX F

NURSES' PERCEPTIONS SURVEY TOOL

Survey Questionnaire: Please complete and return this survey by December 11, 2017.

Date: _____

Please select a number that best represents your perceptions of the checklist tool.

1=Strongly Disagree 3= Neutral 5=Strongly Agree
2= Disagree 4=Agree

- | | |
|---|-------------------|
| 1) The checklist identified the critical safety components for the transition of care | 1 2 3 4 5 |
| 2) The checklist tool is easy to use | 1 2 3 4 5 |
| 3) The checklist tool will improve communication between pre-operative and intraoperative areas | 1 2 3 4 5 |
| 4) I am likely to recommend the checklist tool for implementation | 1 2 3 4 5 |
| 5) The time added by using the structured hand off checklist was valuable | 1 2 3 4 5 |
| 6) Aside from patient identification, allergies, procedure, site/side, laboratory, and diagnostic tests verifications, do you have recommendations for item (s) that should be added to and/or deleted from the checklist tool? | |
| 7) Please list any suggestions or feedback. | |

Thank you for your participation in this effort to improve our department.

APPENDIX G

DAILY LEADERSHIP OBSERVATION AUDIT TOOL

Date-
Time-
Observer-

- 1) Is there a nurse-to-nurse hand off? Yes/ No
 (one pre-operative and one intra-operative)
 Comments: _____
- 2) Is the checklist tool at its designated location? Yes/ No
 (on the front of the chart)
 Comments: _____
- 3) Were all the checklist components addressed? Yes/ No
 a) If no, which items were not addressed? _____
 b) How many items were not addressed? _____
 Comments: _____
- 4) Did both nurses sign off the checklist? Yes/ No
 Comments: _____

Note:

Instructions: Each auditor will observe a hand off process without coaching or participating. The participants (nurses) will not be aware they are being observed. The auditor will be in a location, which provides an opportunity to see and hear the structured hand off process.

APPENDIX H

DAILY PRE-OPERATIVE AUDIT CHECKLIST

Daily Pre-operative Audit Checklist

Month of: August

	WEEK 1					WEEK 2					WEEK 3					WEEK 4					WEEK 5					Totals
	M	T	W	Th	F	M	T	W	Th	F	M	T	W	Th	F	M	T	W	Th	F	M	T	W	Th	F	
		1	2	3	4	7	8	9	10	11	14	15	16	17	18	21	22	23	24	25	28	29	30	31		
Number of Elective Cases Performed from 7:15 AM - 3:00 PM		13	12	17	13	8	10	13	18	10	11	15	15	11	13	12	10	15	13	14	11	15	16	14		
Number of accurate checklist tool.		13	11	13	12	7	10	11	18	9	9	15	13	11	11	10	8	14	11	11	11	15	13	14		
Number of incomplete checklist tool.		0	1	4	1	1	0	2	0	1	2	0	2	0	2	2	2	1	2	3	0	0	3	0		
Number of reported documented clinical events.		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		

90%

APPENDIX I

DAILY LEADERSHIP OBSERVATION TALLY TOOL

Daily Leadership Observation Tally Tool

Month of: August

	AUDITOR	WEEK 1					WEEK 2					WEEK 3					WEEK 3					WEEK 5					% Totals						
		M	T	W	Th	F	M	T	W	Th	F	M	T	W	Th	F	M	T	W	Th	F	M	T	W	Th	F							
Is there a nurse-to-nurse handoff?	1		Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	100.0%
	2		Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	100.0%
	3		Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	100.0%
Is the checklist tool at its designated location?	1		Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	100.0%
	2		Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	100.0%
	3		Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	100.0%
Are the checklist components addressed/checked?	1		Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	84.2%
	2		Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	100.0%
	3		Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	100.0%
Did both nurses sign off on the checklist?	1		Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	100.0%
	2		Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	100.0%
	3		Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	100.0%

AUDITOR COLUMN KEY **1** = DNP Author **2** =Nurse Manager **3** = Nurse Lead

RESULTS KEY = Candidates Days Off **Y** = Answered Yes **N** = Answered No

APPENDIX J

EDUCATION PLAN

PERIOPERATIVE CHECKLIST TOOL EDUCATIONAL PLAN

Objectives:

- 1) To educate pre-operative and intra-operative nurses in the outpatient surgery department regarding the DNP author's pilot project.
 - a) Purpose of the project
 - b) Inclusion and exclusion criteria of the project
 - c) Timeline
 - d) Stakeholders
 - e) Overview of the checklist
 - f) Structured hand off process
 - g) Audits
 - h) Survey
- 2) To gain the commitment of the pre-operative and intra-operative nurses in the outpatient surgery department to participate in the pilot project.
- 3) To explain the correlation between the DNP author's project and improvement of patient care in the outpatient surgery department.
- 4) To clarify any questions or unclear information related to the pilot project.

Who: Bernadette Roberson, RN, MSN, CNOR (DNP author) will conduct the education.

When: October 16, 2017 from 6:35 AM-7: 15 AM

Where: Outpatient Surgery Center Staff Lounge

Attendees: Pre-operative and Intra-operative Nurses scheduled from 7:00 AM-3:00 PM, nurse manager, and nurse lead of the surgery outpatient department.

Handouts: Copy of the checklist tool will be distributed to the nurses.

Purpose of the Project:

The purpose of this DNP project is to create a process to improve nurse-to-nurse communication and reporting of critical patient information to ensure a safe transition between pre-operative and intra-operative settings.

The DNP candidate has chosen this quality improvement project to fulfill a requirement to graduate as a DNP.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria of the Project:

- 1) Inclusion- Elective cases scheduled at the outpatient surgery department from 7:15 AM to 3:00 PM.
- 2) Exclusion- Cases after 3:00 PM and any cases added during the day.

Timeline of the Project:

- 1) October 1, 2017- October 31, 2017
 - a) Development and approval of the checklist tool by the expert panels.
- 2) November 1, 2017-November 30, 2017
 - a) Implementation of the checklist tool for the hand off between pre-operative nurses to the intra-operative nurses.
 - b) Daily Perioperative Checklist Tool audits
 - c) Daily leadership rounding audits
- 3) December 1, 2017-December 31, 2017
 - a) Nurses' Perceptions Survey
 - b) Evaluation of the pilot study
 - c) Continue usage of the checklist for continuity of the hand off process

Stakeholders:

- 1) Pre-operative and Intra-operative nurses working from 7:00 AM to 3:00 PM
- 2) Nurse manager
- 3) Nurse lead
- 4) Safety Committee-expert panels

Overview of the Checklist:

- 1) Reliability of the checklist tool –based upon the Universal Protocol from The Joint Commission (https://www.jointcommission.org/assets/1/18/UP_Poster1.PDF).
- 2) Review of the actual checklist step by step

Structured Hand off Process:

- 1) The Pre-operative Checklist Tool will be part of the of the pre-operative packet and will be clipped onto the top of the chart.
- 2) The pre-operative nurses and intra-operative nurses will conduct the transfer of patient information.
- 3) The transfer of information to be conducted in the pre-operative area prior to patient transport to the intra-operative area.
- 4) The Pre-operative checklist tool will be utilized during the transfer of information.
- 5) The intra-operative nurses will be required to check the boxes of all components addressed during the transition of care.
- 6) The secured location to drop the completed checklist tool will be decided at this meeting.

- 7) The intra-operative nurses will drop the checklist to the secured predetermined location.

Audits:

- 1) The manager of the outpatient surgery department will conduct the daily Pre-operative checklist audits. This is to validate the effectiveness and reliability of the checklist tool.
- 2) The DNP author, manager, and lead of the outpatient surgery department will conduct the daily leadership observation audits. This is for leadership to validate the structured hand off process is being followed.

Survey:

- 1) The nurses' perception survey will be conducted on December 5, 2017- December 11, 2017.
- 2) Nurses will not be required to provide their names.
- 3) Four Likert Scale and two narrative questions will be used for the survey.
- 4) A locked drop box will be available outside the manager office for submission.

Correlation of the Project to Quality Care:

1) Provide frequency data of reported events collected by the Risk Department related to communication breakdowns from January 1, 2016 to December 31, 2016 specific for the pre-operative to intra-operative areas of the outpatient surgery department.

Questions and Answers- last remaining minutes of the meeting.

B. Roberson 4/22/17

APPENDIX K

DRAFTED PRE-OPERATIVE CHECKLIST

PRE-OPERATIVE CHECKLIST TOOL

1) Patient Verification:

Name DOB MRN (last 3 digits)

2) NPO Status Verification: _____ *time* **3) Allergies Verification:**

4) Procedural Verification (procedure in all areas must be the same):

Order Consent History and Physical Schedule

5) Site/Side Verification: Right Left Surgeon Marked

6) Pre-operative Medication:

Oral _____ *time* IV _____ *time*

7) Labs:

8) EKG:

9) Other Diagnostic Tests: Radiology Images Scans Biopsies

Pathology

10) Review of Medications: **11)**

Implants/Pacemaker/ICD:

13) Language English **Other(s)**_____

14) Hearing /Visual /Learning Barriers: List_____ N/A

15) Past Medical History:

Each RN to initial: Pre-operative RN _____ Intra-Operative

RN_____

Modified from Universal Protocol /The Joint Commission (2017)

B/Roberson 4/22/17

APPENDIX L
REVISED PRE-OPERATIVE CHECKLIST

Pre-Operative Checklist

1. Patient Verification

- Name
- DOB
- MRN (last three digits)

2. Allergies Verification

3. Review of Medications

- Pre-op Meds Given

4. NPO Status Verification

5. Past Medical History Reviewed

6. Procedure Verification

- Order
- Consent
- History and Physical
- Schedule
- Site Marked (if applicable)

7. Labs

8. EKG

9. Other (Circle all that are applicable)

Barriers: Hearing Visual Learning
Language

Pacemaker ICD Non-Removable Jewelry

Limb Alert OIB Fall Risk

Pre-Operative RN Initial _____

Intra-Operative RN Initial _____